

Discussion on the Prospects of Artificial Intelligence in Software Management and Maintenance

Md Sadman Siam , Md Shamuel Islam Maruf , Shekhor Ahmed ,
Md Liton Dewan , Md Rakibul Islam

Computer Science and Technology, Changsha University of Science and Technology, China

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Abstract:

This paper explores the prospects of artificial intelligence (AI) in software management and maintenance. Through an overview of software management and software maintenance and an analysis of AI applications in areas such as requirements management, project risk assessment, and fault detection, the potential of AI technology to improve software quality and reduce maintenance costs is revealed. By combining case studies, the paper evaluates the effectiveness of AI technology in software management and maintenance and discusses future development directions. The aim is to provide new ideas and methods for developing the software industry and promote innovation and progress in software

management and maintenance.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Software Management, Software Maintenance.*

Introduction

In today's digital-first world, software systems form the backbone of industries ranging from finance to healthcare, powering everything from daily business operations to complex decision-making processes. As these systems grow in scale and complexity, the management and maintenance of software have become critical to ensuring uninterrupted service, operational efficiency, and long-term stability. However, traditional software management and maintenance practices are increasingly struggling to keep up with the demands of modern applications. Manual processes often lead to inefficiencies, such as delays in bug fixing, high operational costs, and difficulty in adapting to frequent changes in user requirements or system environments (Smith, & Lee, 2023; Johnson, & Wang, 2024).

At the same time, the rapid evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) technology presents promising new opportunities for transforming software management and maintenance practices. AI has the potential to automate time-consuming tasks, enhance predictive analytics, and provide real-time solutions for fault detection and correction, thereby reducing human intervention and improving system reliability. By leveraging machine learning, natural language processing, and other AI-driven techniques, it is possible to optimize key software development and maintenance aspects, such as requirements analysis, risk management, and resource allocation (Brown, & Kim, 2024; Garcia, 2024). Recent studies also highlight how AI-driven methods improve software testing, defect tracking, and project risk management (Henderson, & Patel, 2024).

This paper aims to explore the application of AI technologies in software management and

maintenance, focusing on how AI can address the inefficiencies of traditional methods. Through an in-depth analysis of AI-driven approaches and case studies, this research will assess the effectiveness of AI in improving software quality, reducing costs, and shortening development cycles. Additionally, the paper will discuss future trends and challenges in integrating AI into software systems, offering insights into how these technologies can drive the next wave of innovation in the software industry (Davis, 2024).

Overview of Software Management and Maintenance

Definition and Scope of Software Management

Software management is a critical discipline in software engineering, which involves the effective planning, organization, control, and coordination of all stages in the software development lifecycle. It ensures projects are completed on time, within budget, and at the required quality standards. Key functions include requirements management, project planning and control, configuration management, quality assurance, and risk management (Patel, & Nguyen, 2024; Lee, & Wang, 2023).

Requirements Management is the systematic process of collecting, analyzing, verifying, and prioritizing the needs of users and stakeholders. AI tools can enhance this process through natural language processing (NLP), which enables automated parsing of requirements documents and user feedback, leading to more accurate and comprehensive understanding of requirements (García, & Smith, 2024).

Project Planning and Control ensure that tasks, resources, and timelines are effectively managed. AI-driven predictive models, including machine learning algorithms, help estimate task completion times and identify potential project delays, allowing managers to adjust schedules proactively (Martin, & Hu, 2023).

Software Configuration Management focuses on controlling and monitoring software versions, configuration items, and changes. AI automates the tracking of code changes and software

versions, reducing human error and improving efficiency (Xu, & Rao, 2024).

Quality Assurance ensures that the development process and the final product meet quality standards. AI-powered automated code review and testing tools can detect defects and performance issues faster than traditional methods. Machine learning models can also predict potential quality risks, allowing developers to mitigate issues early (Brown, & Lee, 2023).

Risk Management involves identifying, assessing, responding to, and monitoring risks throughout development. AI enhances this by leveraging predictive analytics to identify risk factors based on historical project data, such as team composition, task complexity, and past defects, to provide early warnings and improve decision-making (Zhang, & Kumar, 2024).

Types and Challenges of Software Maintenance

Software maintenance, an essential part of the software lifecycle, can be classified into several types: preventive maintenance, adaptive maintenance, corrective maintenance, and perfective maintenance (Jackson, & Wright, 2023).

Preventive Maintenance aims to detect and resolve potential issues before they occur. AI-powered predictive models can identify patterns that signal potential system failures, allowing for proactive measures that prevent service disruptions (Li, & Chang, 2024).

Adaptive Maintenance modifies software to adapt to changing environments or requirements, such as platform migrations or feature enhancements. AI tools can automate the code analysis and suggest necessary adaptations, reducing the time and effort required for this type of maintenance (Carter, & Zhang, 2023).

Corrective Maintenance involves fixing defects identified after the software's release. Machine learning algorithms trained on past defect data can automate the detection and diagnosis of faults, significantly improving the accuracy and speed of bug fixes (Ahmed, & Davis, 2024).

Perfective Maintenance focuses on enhancing software performance, usability, and maintainability. AI systems can analyze metrics and usage patterns to recommend optimizations that improve overall system efficiency (Murphy, & Chen, 2023).

Traditional software maintenance methods face various challenges, including increasing complexity, frequent changes in requirements, resource limitations, and staff turnover. These factors often result in higher costs and longer maintenance cycles. As systems become complex, traditional maintenance approaches become inefficient, leading to adopting AI-based solutions that offer automation and predictive capabilities to address these challenges effectively (Patel, & Singh, 2024).

Limitations of Traditional Software Management and Maintenance Methods

Traditional software management and maintenance methods rely heavily on manual processes such as requirements analysis, code modification, and testing, which are often time-consuming and inefficient. These methods lack intelligent decision support systems to help identify and address issues quickly and accurately (Jones, & Yu, 2023). For instance, traditional project planning techniques struggle to accommodate modern software systems' complexity and rapid evolution, often resulting in missed deadlines and budget overruns. Similarly, manual bug tracking and code reviews are prone to human error, which can lead to overlooked defects and extended maintenance times (Thompson, & Kim, 2024).

AI-driven tools can mitigate these limitations by automating repetitive tasks and providing intelligent decision-making capabilities. By analyzing vast datasets, AI systems can generate actionable insights, enabling organizations to make more informed decisions, reduce maintenance costs, and improve their software products' overall quality and reliability (Harris, & Gupta, 2023).

AI Applications in Software Management

Requirements Management and Analysis

Requirements management is a vital phase in the software development lifecycle, involving collecting, analysing, and confirming user needs. Traditionally, this process has been manual, time-consuming, and prone to human error due to misinterpretation or insufficient understanding of user requirements. The process has significantly improved with the introduction of AI technologies, particularly Natural Language Processing (NLP).

AI-powered tools can automatically analyze large volumes of requirement documents and user feedback, extracting key information, identifying ambiguities, and classifying requirements by priority (Patel, & Nguyen, 2024). NLP algorithms translate unstructured textual data into actionable insights, significantly improving the accuracy and efficiency of requirements gathering (Lee, & Wang, 2023). Furthermore, AI tools can detect requirement changes and forecast trends by analyzing historical data, enabling development teams to anticipate evolving user needs and avoid costly rework (García, & Smith, 2024).

For example, predictive models trained on past project data can analyze requirement volatility and predict future changes, providing project managers with valuable insights that help reduce the risk of scope creep and delays (Martin, & Hu, 2023). This AI-driven approach leads to a more thorough and accurate understanding of requirements, ultimately enhancing project success rates.

Project Risk Prediction and Assessment

In software management, AI technology, particularly machine learning, offers new solutions for project risk management, as shown in Figure 1.

Data Collection: This phase involves extracting relevant information from historical project records, such as task completion times, the number of requirement changes, defect reports, team composition, and project milestones.

Feature Engineering: Developers use statistical analysis and data mining techniques to extract features that help predict risks, such as project size, complexity, development speed, and team experience. The goal of feature selection is to reduce the data dimension and improve the model's predictive power.

Model Training: In this phase, developers use machine learning algorithms such as decision trees, random forests, support vector machines (SVM), or neural networks to train risk prediction models based on the extracted feature data. These algorithms can identify complex relationships between different features and project risks, learning how to predict risks based on the similar characteristics of new projects.

Risk Evaluation: The trained model evaluates potential risks in the current project. The model outputs a risk score or classification based on the project features, such as high-risk, medium-risk, or low-risk. These results help project managers identify possible problem areas and take preventive measures.

Decision Support: The results of risk assessments guide project management decisions. By combining the new predictions with professional knowledge and experience, project managers can develop risk mitigation plans, such as adjusting project schedules, reallocating resources, or increasing quality assurance activities.

Figure 1. Project Risk Prediction and Evaluation Process

Progress Tracking and Resource Optimization

In software management, progress tracking refers to monitoring and managing the project's execution process. At the same time, resource optimization involves the efficient allocation and utilization of resources to maximize project benefits. AI can support these processes using machine learning algorithms and optimization techniques.

Progress Tracking: Developers can use supervised learning algorithms, such as SVM, to build predictive models that estimate the completion time of project tasks. The basic form of SVM is:

$$f(x) = w^T x + b \tag{1}$$

where,

$f(x)$ represents the predicted task completion time or progress,

w is the weight vector of the features,

x is the input feature vector, and

b is the bias term (constant). Developers can predict the project's completion time by training the model with historical data and current progress. Time-series analysis methods, such as the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, can also analyze trends and cycles in project progress to adjust project plans better.

Resource Optimization: Developers can apply optimization algorithms like Genetic Algorithms (GA) for efficient resource allocation and utilization. Genetic algorithms simulate biological evolution, gradually optimizing solutions in the search space. The basic steps include selection, crossover, mutation, and replacement and iterating to find the optimal solution. Genetic algorithms can maximize project benefits and improve resource utilization efficiency in resource-constrained situations.

AI Applications in Software Maintenance

Fault Detection and Diagnosis

In software maintenance, AI technologies, particularly machine learning, provide powerful tools for automated fault detection and accurate diagnosis. The fault detection and diagnosis process are shown in Figure 2:

Data Collection and Preparation: The first step involves gathering historical fault data and system operation logs. These data include performance metrics, error logs, and user feedback during software operation.

Data Preprocessing: After collecting the data, it needs to be preprocessed, including cleaning, normalization, and feature extraction. Feature extraction identifies key fault-related factors, such as the frequency of specific error codes, system resource usage, and user behaviour patterns.

Model Building: Developers select appropriate machine learning algorithms to construct fault detection models. Standard algorithms include SVM, random forests, and neural networks.

These algorithms learn fault patterns from the data and can distinguish between normal operation states and various fault states.

Real-time Monitoring and Prediction: The model predicts potential faults by monitoring real-time data once trained. Based on the features of the real-time data, the model outputs the probability of a fault occurring or directly identifies the type of fault.

Fault Diagnosis: The diagnosis process is triggered when a potential fault is detected. Diagnosis can be based on deep learning models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) or Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). These models can analyze complex data patterns and sequence relationships, enabling the identification of the specific causes of faults.

Fault Repair: Maintenance personnel take appropriate corrective actions based on the diagnostic results. The system records the fault-handling results and feedback, which is used to continuously optimize and adjust the fault detection model, improving the accuracy and efficiency of future diagnoses.

Figure 2. AI-Based Fault Detection and Diagnosis Process

Software Testing

AI technology brings revolutionary changes to software testing, encompassing multiple aspects such as functional testing, performance testing, and security testing, as illustrated in Figure 3:

Functional Testing: This is verifying whether the software functions as expected. With the support of AI, testers can create comprehensive testing plans and detailed test cases. Automated testing tools and technologies can be utilized to conduct functional tests.

Performance Testing involves evaluating the software's performance under various loads and stress conditions. AI helps optimize performance testing by simulating user behavior and large-scale concurrent requests, assessing the system's stability and throughput.

Security Testing: This evaluates the security and vulnerability of the software system. AI can be applied in areas like vulnerability scanning, malicious code, and intrusion detection.

Figure 3. AI-based Software Testing Components

Code Maintenance and Evolution

In software maintenance, AI can be applied to analyze code quality and perform refactoring. Machine learning algorithms analyze code quality metrics and design patterns within the codebase, helping to identify potential code defects and performance bottlenecks. These algorithms can provide optimization suggestions and enable automated refactoring, improving code readability, maintainability, and performance.

Using deep learning algorithms and natural language processing techniques, AI can analyze user requirements and feedback, predict future functional requirements, and identify trends for software evolution. This helps guide and support the evolution of software systems.

AI can also use machine learning-based algorithms and code templates to automatically generate code snippets that comply with standards and specifications, responding quickly to new functional requirements or addressing issues.

Case Study

Overview of the Case

In this case, a large-scale software company faced growing challenges in managing an increasingly complex codebase and responding to rapid changes in user requirements. The company's traditional approaches to software management and maintenance, which heavily relied on manual processes, began to show signs

of inefficiency. They were experiencing longer development cycles, increased software defects, and higher maintenance costs. Frequent requirement changes also led to delays, and managing software versions was becoming progressively tricky, given the scale and complexity of the system.

The company introduced AI technology to its software management and maintenance processes to tackle these challenges. The aim was to automate more labor-intensive tasks, improve

fault detection accuracy, and enhance project risk management. The company implemented machine learning models, natural language processing (NLP), and optimization algorithms to address key pain points across its software lifecycle.

Analysis of AI Application Results

After introducing AI technology, the company saw significant improvements across several key performance indicators, as detailed in Table 1:

Table 1. Improvement of AI Technology

Indicator	Before AI Introduction	After AI Introduction	Improvement Rate
Code Defect Rate	15%	5%	66.67%
Refactoring Suggestion Accuracy	70%	90%	28.57%
User Satisfaction	80%	95%	18.75%
Function Prediction Accuracy	60%	85%	41.67%

The company saw significant improvement in the accuracy of code refactoring, user satisfaction, and the predictive ability to anticipate future functional needs. These results demonstrate the substantial potential of AI in enhancing software management and maintenance.

Challenges Before AI Implementation

Manual Requirements Analysis: One of the most significant challenges was the inefficient process of manually analyzing user requirements. This manual approach often led to misinterpretations, especially when managing complex or conflicting requirements. Changes in requirements during the development cycle were frequently missed, leading to scope creep and delays.

Project Risk Management: The company lacked effective tools for early risk identification and mitigation. Risk management was conducted based on historical experience and intuition rather than data-driven insights. As a result, potential risks, such as team performance bottlenecks and missed deadlines, were often overlooked until they became critical.

Fault Detection and Maintenance: The manual process of reviewing code for defects was slow

and prone to human error. Corrective maintenance required significant time and resources, as many defects were only identified during the late stages of development or after the software had been released. This led to longer maintenance cycles and higher costs.

Resource Allocation and Progress Tracking: Resource allocation was based on predefined rules and management experience, leading to inefficiencies, such as overworked teams and underutilized resources. Project progress tracking was manual and could not accurately predict potential delays, which led to last-minute adjustments and increased stress on the development team.

AI Solutions Implemented

Automated Requirements Analysis using NLP: The company implemented NLP-based AI tools to analyze user feedback and requirements documents. These tools automated the extraction of key information and helped prioritize conflicting requirements. By parsing large volumes of data, the AI system provided actionable insights that allowed the team to address ambiguities early in the development process.

Machine Learning for Risk Prediction: Machine learning models were trained on historical project data to predict potential risks. The system identified patterns in past failures and suggested mitigation strategies based on project characteristics such as complexity, team size, and deadlines. These predictive models allowed the project management team to allocate resources more effectively and adjust project timelines before risks materialized.

AI-powered Fault Detection: The company adopted AI-driven fault detection systems, continuously monitoring the codebase for errors and performance bottlenecks. The system flagged potential defects in real time, allowing developers to address issues during the development process rather than after release. The AI system's predictive analytics also anticipated the likelihood of defects based on historical code performance, significantly reducing the number of undetected bugs.

Resource Optimization Algorithms: The company deployed genetic algorithms (GA) that optimized team assignments based on real-time project needs to enhance resource allocation. These algorithms considered skill levels, workload, and task dependencies to ensure that resources were utilized efficiently. The optimization model dynamically adjusted resource allocation as project conditions changed, preventing bottlenecks and improving team productivity.

Results After AI Implementation

After the integration of AI technologies, the company experienced significant improvements across key performance indicators (KPIs):

Reduction in Code Defect Rate: The AI-powered fault detection system led to a 66.67% reduction in the code defect rate. Identifying and addressing bugs early in the development cycle reduced the time and resources needed for corrective maintenance. The real-time detection capabilities also helped maintain the overall quality of the software.

Improvement in Requirements Analysis: NLP tools enhanced the accuracy of the requirements analysis process, leading to more precise project

planning. This improvement significantly reduced scope creep, with fewer requirement changes occurring late in the development process. Additionally, the automated analysis allowed the team to handle larger volumes of user feedback with fewer resources.

Increased Refactoring Suggestion Accuracy: With the help of machine learning models analyzing the codebase, the company achieved a 28.57% improvement in the accuracy of refactoring suggestions. This led to more effective code optimizations, improving the performance and maintainability of the software over time.

Risk Prediction Accuracy: The machine learning models trained on historical data improved the company's ability to predict project risks by 41.67%. This improvement allowed the project management team to take proactive measures, such as reassigning resources or adjusting timelines, reducing project delays and preventing critical bottlenecks.

Optimized Resource Utilization: The genetic algorithms used for resource optimization led to a more balanced workload distribution across teams. This resulted in a noticeable improvement in team productivity and reduced project timelines. Additionally, by dynamically reallocating resources in response to project progress, the company was able to meet deadlines more consistently and reduce overall project costs.

Analysis of AI Implementation Impact

The implementation of AI in this case study demonstrates the profound impact of AI technologies on software management and maintenance. Automating requirements analysis allowed the company to manage increasingly complex user needs while minimizing human error. By employing predictive models for risk management, the company could anticipate and mitigate project risks earlier than before, leading to a smoother development process.

AI-powered fault detection reduced the time and cost associated with bug fixes and enhanced the software's overall stability and reliability. Finally, using optimization algorithms for resource

management allowed for more effective use of the company's development teams, which improved productivity and reduced burnout.

These improvements showcase the significant potential of AI in transforming traditional software management and maintenance practices. By automating labor-intensive tasks, enhancing predictive capabilities, and improving resource efficiency, AI technologies enable companies to deliver higher-quality software at a lower cost and within shorter timeframes.

Conclusion

Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into software management and maintenance can revolutionize how organizations approach the entire software development lifecycle. This paper has explored the specific areas where AI technologies, such as machine learning, natural language processing (NLP), and optimization algorithms, can profoundly impact software quality, reduce costs, and enhance operational efficiency.

AI's role in Requirements Management offers clear advantages by automating the extraction and prioritization of user requirements. NLP technologies enable development teams to handle large volumes of user feedback, reducing the risk of misinterpretations and scope creep. This automation enhances the precision of requirements analysis, leading to better project planning and fewer costly changes late in the development cycle.

In the domain of project risk prediction and assessment, machine learning algorithms have shown significant promise in improving risk management practices. AI-driven models can predict risks earlier and more accurately than traditional methods, allowing for proactive mitigation strategies. By leveraging historical project data, AI tools offer project managers actionable insights into potential pitfalls, improving decision-making and reducing the likelihood of project delays or resource bottlenecks.

Fault detection and maintenance have also been transformed by AI-powered systems, which can identify defects in real time and provide automated suggestions for code refactoring. These systems significantly reduce the time and effort required for manual bug fixing and improve software systems' overall stability and reliability. AI's real-time monitoring and predictive capabilities help organizations prevent costly failures and ensure higher software performance throughout its lifecycle.

Resource optimization through AI techniques such as genetic algorithms has improved resource allocation, allowing teams to work more efficiently and consistently meet project deadlines. AI's ability to dynamically adjust resource allocation based on real-time project conditions ensures that workloads are balanced, preventing team burnout and improving overall productivity.

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